

Incorporating hyperspectral data into variable rate fertiliser plans for NZ hill country

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Background

Precision aerial fertiliser application using GIS guidance and automated fertiliser hopper control allows application rates to better match the requirements of individual hill country landscape units which vary in productivity and soil fertility. Remote sensing using hyperspectral imaging technology is showing promise as a tool to determine soil fertility attributes and to classify vegetation across hill country landscapes. This data is being used in combination with models of pastoral productivity and fertiliser responsiveness to create precision fertiliser application maps.

Methods

To determine the optimal nutrient status and fertiliser requirement of landscape units we use GIS landscape analysis, pasture growth modelling, remotely sensed soil fertility and vegetation layers, and econometric analysis. This paper describes the application of the suite of analytical tools to Pati Tapu Station, a 2623ha hill country station in the southern North Island, New Zealand. Pati Tapu Station runs 16000 sheep and 3700 beef stock units. Six management blocks were defined based on topography, fertiliser history, stock management and productivity. The farmer's set stocking rates over the lambing period were used to assess the relative productivity of each block. The Overseer[®] nutrient budget model (<https://www.overseer.org.nz/>) was used to collate the farm information and calculate block stocking rates.

High resolution hyperspectral remote sensing data was used to define areas of pasture in contrast to other vegetation types such as native bush, pine forest, bare soil and waterbodies at a resolution of 1m² pixels (Cushnahan *et al.* 2017). To create an effective area map suitable for aerial fertiliser application, this vegetation layer was processed by calculating the proportion of 1m² pasture pixels in 100m² grid cells. Where there was greater than 50% pasture the grid cell was classified as pasture. This was then simplified by eliminating small areas of either pasture or non-pasture less than 0.5ha and narrow areas less than approximately 70m in width.

GIS analysis was used to define land units within each management block with similar slope, aspect, altitude and soil type. Land units with the same attributes were combined to form landforms.

The Pasture Growth Forecaster model (<http://www.pasturegrowthforecaster.co.nz/>), which is a hybrid model containing the McCall pasture growth model as revised by Romera *et al.* (2009) and the soil moisture balance developed by Woodward *et al.* (2001), was further adapted for site specific hill country use. The modified pasture growth model was used to estimate the effect of topography and soil properties on potential productivity of landforms within management blocks. The impact of management factors such as the degree of subdivision and pasture utilisation on stocking rates were accounted for by the farmer's estimate of the relative productivity of each management block. On Pati Tapu Station set stocking rates over the lambing period were used as the basis for defining the block relativity.

A high resolution Olsen P soil fertility map was derived from the hyperspectral remote sensing data (Yule, McVeigh, Pullangari *pers. comm.*). In a validation study on the farm 5 of 6 transects had a predicted Olsen P within 3 units of the soil test result. There was a high degree of skewness in the 1m² resolution estimates with a small proportion of total area having Olsen P levels in the 50 to 75 range. In conventional soil sampling for fertiliser recommendations fertility hotspots such as stock camps are deliberately avoided, and in terms of fertiliser planning there is a nil P requirement when Olsen P soil test levels are very high. Hence to avoid the impact of very localised high soil fertility

estimates biasing the average of adjoining areas we truncated the predicted Olsen P distribution at a level of 50.

Predicted Olsen P values were then averaged across land units. The soil test levels for K and S were determined from conventional sampling.

Areas with similar levels of potential productivity, soil fertility, soil order (the highest level of soil classification in New Zealand which affects the interpretation of soil test results), topography and management were then grouped into soil fertility production units for the purpose of establishing nutrient requirements using the Overseer[®] nutrient budget model and the Fertiliser Association of NZ Econometric model (Metherell *et al.* 1996).

Overseer was used to model current management, estimate the stocking rate on each soil fertility production unit and provide the biophysical inputs for the Econometric model. On ground fertiliser costs, including transport and spreading, were used to estimate the value of the individual nutrients (P, K and S). Gross margins for sheep and beef stock classes were calculated from farm financial data for animal and wool sales, and input costs including animal health, shearing and freight. A time preference rate or discount is chosen based on the cost of farm borrowing minus the inflation rate. The Econometric model calculates the annual nutrient inputs required to maximise the long term net present value of the returns from animal production minus the cost of fertiliser inputs. An optimal strategy may result in maintenance of soil fertility levels for parts of the farm, an increase in soil fertility and animal stocking rate requiring capital fertiliser or a decrease in soil fertility and stocking rate achieved by withholding fertiliser. Using the Econometric model the optimal Olsen P status and the rate of P fertiliser required to move the current fertility level to the optimum were calculated for each soil fertility production unit. For the purpose of the analysis presented here it was assumed that there was no budget constraint on fertiliser expenditure. Sulphur and potassium requirements were also estimated by the Econometric model, although in this case there was no K requirement.

The optimal rates of the nutrients P and S were then generalised into a fertiliser plan which is practical for aerial application. A key consideration is that a limited number of fertiliser products can be used, even although the theoretical optimum P:S ratio might vary widely. The main fertiliser product manufactured and used in New Zealand is superphosphate with a P:S ratio of 9:11. A range of sulphur fortified superphosphate products are also manufactured or blended for use when the S requirement is substantially larger than the P requirement. Given that most of Pati Tapu has a relatively low S status, there is an S requirement over the whole farm. For part of the farm which had a nil or low P requirement, we chose to use a sulphur fortified superphosphate with a P:S ratio of 8:20 at a minimum rate of 100 kg/ha to provide at least 20 kg S /ha. For the majority of the farm where most areas had higher P than S requirements we chose to use superphosphate. A direct translation of the P requirement of each landunit into a fertiliser rate results in an application map which is too complex for practical aerial application, as it is not feasible to have the fertiliser hopper in the topdressing plane changing the flow rate over very short distances. Hence it was necessary to further generalise the fertiliser rate map using a variety of GIS data processing techniques. The resultant map was used to calculate the total quantity required for each of the two fertiliser products.

Results

Figure 1 shows the Olsen P estimation map clipped to the pasture area, both of which were derived from the hyperspectral data. The optimum Olsen P level, taking into account the productive potential of each landform, the applied cost of P fertiliser and the long term economic return, is shown in Figure 2.

The optimal year one P application rates to move from the current to the optimal Olsen P level, plus maintenance P if required, is shown in Figure 3. Figure 4 shows a practical fertiliser application map utilising two products. The areas to be topdressed with superphosphate and sulphur super 20 and their application rates are shown in Table 1. The total quantity of fertiliser required to apply this plan is 625 tonnes superphosphate plus 40 tonnes of Sulphur Super 20, which is approximately a 50% increase on the previous year's application. In subsequent years a different fertiliser plan would be applied to maintain the optimal fertility status.

Figure 1. Olsen P predicted from hyperspectral imaging remote sensing, clipped to the pasture area

Figure 2. Optimum Olsen P predicted by Econometric modelling

Figure 3. Optimum year 1 fertiliser P predicted by Econometric modelling

Figure 4. Proposed fertiliser application plan

Product	Rate (kg/ha)	Area (ha)	Tonnes
Superphosphate	100	459.1	
	200	297.7	
	300	13.1	
	400	98.0	
	500	214.8	
	600	55.4	
	700	51.9	
	800	196.4	
	900	83.4	
	1000	67.3	
	Total	1537.1	625.0
Sulphur Super 20	100	48.2	
	200	176.7	
	Total	224.9	40.2

Table 1. Summary of the rates of two fertiliser products required to achieve a practically feasible optimal variable rate fertiliser plan for aerial application

Discussion

Despite the ability of the remote sensed and GIS data layers and decision support models to generate a very detailed nutrient requirement map, a number of generalisation steps are required to produce a practical fertiliser plan. Some pragmatic decisions must also be made in the choice of fertiliser product and the parts of the farm to which each product will be applied, as it is not realistic to be applying different products to spatially separated small areas of the farm.

Given the increase in fertiliser required to meet the proposed plan, a discussion with the farmer would need to be held to decide whether the plan is financially feasible given that fertiliser is only one item of farm expenditure and that an increase in farm stocking rate or stock production levels would also be required to reap the benefit of increased fertility levels. An option with little impact on overall profitability would be to spread the capital expenditure over two or more years.

The plan may also need to be modified in order to meet environmental constraints. It is relatively straight forward to incorporate fertiliser exclusion zones into the application map, but the necessary buffer distance between the zone of fertiliser application and environmentally sensitive water bodies needs to be carefully considered with respect to the ability of the GIS guidance system to control the closing of the fertiliser hopper in an aircraft flying at 200 km per hour, fertiliser ballistics and the effect of wind on fertiliser drift. Current technology requires a buffer zone of about 70m to have a low risk of fertiliser entering an exclusion zone (Chok, *pers. comm.*).

Conclusion

Hyperspectral remote sensing has provided soil fertility and pasture cover data at a very high resolution of 1m² pixels, which need to be generalised and combined with other farm attributes, including soil attributes, potential productivity and farm economics, in order to generate an optimal fertility map. The optimal fertility map must be further generalised to create a variable rate fertiliser plan with one or two products which is feasible for aerial application.

Acknowledgements

We are very grateful to Doug, Jo and Bruce McKenzie of Pati Tapu Station for their willing collaboration and involvement with MPI / Ravensdown's Primary Growth Partnership "Pioneering to Precision" programme; to Tommy Cushnahan for providing the pasture layer; to Reddy Pullangari, Pip McVeigh and Ian Yule for the Olsen P layer; and to Jinjin Ma, Kerry Johns, Keenan Tisch and Kim Saunders for their contribution to modelling and programming the decision support system.

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